

Fiscal Consequences of Corporate Tax Avoidance

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Abstract

Multinational corporations shift a large share of their profits to tax havens and, due to this corporate tax avoidance, governments lose a portion of their tax revenue. We study the consequences of multinational tax avoidance on the structure of government tax revenue. Using German municipal data we analyse how changes in municipal trade tax rates levied on corporate profits affect local tax revenue structure. Following a trade tax rate increase, we find that municipalities with high exposure to aggressive multinationals experience a significant decline in trade tax revenue levels and shares. If they do not compensate for this decline with higher property tax rates and revenues, they experience a decline in overall tax revenues.¹

Keywords: Corporate Tax Avoidance, Profit Shifting, Multinational Corporations, Government Tax Revenue Structure

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1 Introduction

The revelations from Panama and Paradise papers in 2016 and 2017 exposed a sizeable amount of international tax avoidance by firms, and in particular, multinational corporations (MNCs). This spurred renewed interest in the literature to calculate the extent to which MNCs shift profits to tax havens and the scale of potential tax revenue losses to governments (Bilicka; 2019; Tørsløv et al.; 2023; Fuest, Greil, Hugger and Neumeier; 2022; Garcia-Bernardo and Janský; 2024). The estimates from the literature suggest these tax revenue losses are large. In this paper, we ask what are the consequences of these tax avoidance practices on tax revenue structure, i.e., for where governments derive their tax revenues from if they cannot obtain them from multinationals that shift profits. To answer this question, we investigate the effects of corporate tax rate increases mandated by local governments on corporate tax revenues *and* other sources of local tax revenues. In that, we examine whether local governments offset potentially lower corporate tax revenues by raising other tax rates that they control.

To establish a causal relationship between tax avoidance and tax revenue structure, we take advantage of a large variation in municipal trade tax rates across 11,000 municipalities during the period 2008 - 2019 in Germany combined with data on the geographical presence of firms from Orbis Bureau van Dijk. Germany provides a good laboratory to study our question, as municipalities set their own effective trade and property tax *rates*, while the tax *bases* are set by the federal government. During our sample period, the resulting effective trade tax rate varies between 7% and 21%, while the effective property tax rate varies between 3.5% and 33.6%. We specifically focus on the effects of trade tax rate changes, as this tax is levied on corporate profits and it imposes a large burden on firms. The flexibility of local governments in setting two local tax rates independently allows us to further study the complementarity between property and trade tax rates.

Our identification strategy relies on exploring the effects of increases in municipal trade tax rates across municipalities that are differently exposed to MNCs that can plausibly be classified as more tax aggressive.² Using the event study approach, we trace the effects of those trade tax rate increases on the trade tax and overall tax revenues. As a baseline, we compare municipalities that experienced tax rate increases (treated group) to those that did not (control group), following Fuest et al. (2018). To understand the effect of profit shifting on tax revenue structure, we use a triple difference-in-differences approach in which

²Note that 94% of all trade tax rate changes at the municipal level were tax increases during our sample period.

we compare municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs and those that are not relative to the control group before and after a tax rate increase. We define aggressive MNCs as those that have at least one tax haven in their ownership structure, following the large literature, and show our results are also robust to using alternative definitions (Bilicka and Scur; 2021; Davies et al.; 2018; Gumpert et al.; 2016; Hines and Rice; 1994). The local exposure to more aggressive MNCs is defined as a count and a share of subsidiaries that belong to those MNCs relative to the number of all firms in each municipality.³

We find that following a trade tax rate increase at the municipal level, the level of trade tax revenues in municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs falls, even after controlling for trade tax rate, property tax rate, and municipal characteristics. We calculate the elasticity of trade tax revenues with respect to one-minus-the-tax-rate to be -0.775 for those municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs. This elasticity is in line with the elasticities from the literature that estimates the response of a firm’s pre-tax profits and country tax bases to changes in tax rates to be around -1 (Beer et al.; 2020).

The novelty of this paper, relative to that literature, is in understanding the implications of profit shifting for the revenue *structure*. As such, we also consider the effects of trade tax rate increases on total tax revenues and property tax rates and revenues. We find that, when municipalities only increase their trade tax rates, they see a reduction in their overall tax revenues. When municipalities increase the property tax rates at the same time as trade tax rates, they do not experience a decline in overall tax revenues. Instead their property tax revenues also increase, which compensates for the lost trade tax revenue. We further provide supporting evidence that in cases where the overall tax revenue declines, municipalities also reduce their expenditures and increase debt. We show that treated and control municipalities experience a similar evolution of tax revenue structure before the trade tax rate change, but diverge afterward, which allows us to causally interpret our findings. Further, we do not find similar effects for municipalities with a larger share of all MNCs, which we use as a placebo test.

There are two possible mechanisms that can explain why trade tax revenues decline after a trade tax rate increase. First, MNCs may choose to move profits away from municipalities that levy larger taxes on them towards their foreign locations.⁴ Given that profits are mobile across borders, this can potentially be immediately reflected in tax revenues. Second, MNCs

³We also use the share of assets, turnover, and employment these firms have.

⁴Note that given that taxable profits are apportioned according to the share of wages across municipalities within Germany, we would not expect firms to move profits across municipalities. While Riedel (2010) shows that firms do that in Germany before 2008, in our empirical analysis we test this and find no evidence to support that they continue to do it in later time periods that we analyse.

may choose to move their affiliates and/or business operations away from the municipalities that levy higher taxes on them. Further, as [Bilicka, Qi and Xing \(2022\)](#) show, profit shifting may be accompanied by this reallocation of real operations. Both of these effects are likely to be stronger for subsidiaries that belong to more aggressive MNCs. To disentangle the real operations from the profit-shifting mechanism, we consider the effects of trade tax rate hikes on the aggregated firm-level real business operations of MNCs in the treated municipalities. We do not find any evidence for the real operations reallocation mechanism, similar to [Lichter et al. \(2021\)](#). As such, our results suggest that profit shifting is driving the observed decline in the trade tax revenues.

We test the robustness of our findings in three distinct ways. First, instead of firm counts, we use the share of assets, employment, and turnover that subsidiaries which belong to more aggressive MNCs own in each municipality. Our results are consistent with the baseline findings, even though this sample likely overstates the importance of larger firms in each municipality.⁵ Second, given the staggered and heterogeneous nature of the tax rate increases across municipalities, we test the validity of our two-way fixed effects estimates using various newly proposed methods. Our baseline estimates rely on comparing the sample of municipalities that only increased their tax rate once during the sample period to those that did not change their tax rate at all during the sample period. We show that including all of the municipalities does not change our results, as the [Goodman-Bacon \(2021\)](#) decomposition reveals that they mostly rely on the comparison of never treated with treated units. We then provide event study results that account for the negative weights that the staggered and heterogeneous nature of reform introduces by implementing the [Callaway and Sant’Anna \(2021\)](#); [De Chaisemartin and d’Haultfoeuille \(2020\)](#); [Sun and Abraham \(2021\)](#) estimators and find they do not affect our conclusions based on the baseline estimates.

Third, we empirically tackle the issue of tax competition across municipalities. Given the evidence that municipalities, especially smaller ones, can set their tax rates in response to changes in rates of neighbouring municipalities ([Buettner; 2003](#)), we control for neighbouring tax rates, as well as weight our results by population. Again, none of these adjustments significantly change the magnitude of our baseline estimates. Further, [Becker et al. \(2012\)](#) show that German municipalities can use local tax rates to attract *foreign* MNCs as a source of skilled labor, physical capital, and local business tax income. This raises issues of reverse causality when considering the impact of tax rate changes on municipal revenues. However, in our context, competition amongst municipalities for those more aggressive firms is unlikely

⁵This is because predominantly larger subsidiaries report financial information in Orbis data, while domestic firms tend not to report any.

to yield much local business tax revenue, due to the potential profit-shifting activities of those firms. Empirically, we find that following a trade tax rate increase there is no change in the average trade tax rate of municipalities that neighbour the municipality that is exposed to more aggressive MNCs. Hence, we argue that tax competition, and consequently, reverse causality, are not a potential threat to our specific identification strategy.

Our estimates suggest that the ability of firms to shift profits affects the tax revenue structure and has potential distributional consequences. The aggressiveness of MNCs is causally linked with lower revenue levels coming from corporations through the trade tax. As such, profit shifting affects the tax revenue structure and, in particular, the share of revenues coming from corporations. This matters from a policy perspective, as it suggests that municipalities that are more exposed to profit-shifting multinationals, may choose to rely more on non-trade taxes available to them – property taxes. In fact, we show that when municipalities increase their property tax rates in conjunction with trade tax rates, there is no effect of trade tax rate increases on the overall municipal revenue, but when they only change trade tax rates, the overall tax revenue also declines. This has two important consequences. First, to the extent that property taxation can be viewed as more regressive (Crawford et al.; 2010; Decoster et al.; 2010), this may amplify the inequality in municipalities that lose more tax revenue due to profit shifting. Second, as Slemrod and Wilson (2009) theoretically show, imposing higher taxes to recuperate lost corporate revenues is distortionary, as it leads to deadweight loss and reduces welfare.

This paper directly contributes to the literature analysing the effects of tax rate changes on local tax revenues. Fajgelbaum et al. (2019) build a model in which they show that heterogeneity in state tax rates leads to aggregate welfare losses. Suárez Serrato and Zidar (2018) estimate the effects of tax rates and tax bases on the US state tax revenues more generally. Our paper differs in two dimensions. First, we focus on implications of profit shifting for the relationship between tax rates and tax revenues. While these two papers consider the effects of corporate tax rate changes on tax revenues, we show that the direction of this relationship is affected by the types of firms that reside in each locality, especially in terms of their capacity to move profits away from localities imposing higher taxes. Second, unlike in the US, in our setting the municipalities do not set their own tax bases, which means that the only instruments at their disposal are tax rates. This more limited set of instruments allows us to focus on the role of complementarity between different types of tax rates for overall municipal tax revenues.

More broadly, we also build on the existing studies that analyse the magnitude and consequences of profit shifting for tax revenues and other margins (Dharmapala and Riedel;

2013; Dowd et al.; 2017; Grubert and Mutti; 1991; Hines and Rice; 1994; Huizinga and Laeven; 2008; Weichenrieder; 2009; Wier and Erasmus; 2022). First, recent work has estimated the effects of profit shifting on tax revenues lost in developed and developing countries (Garcia-Bernardo and Janský; 2024; Tørsløv et al.; 2023), including the costs of personal and capital gains tax losses (Garcia-Bernardo et al.; 2022). Further, Bilicka (2019) examines the extent of disparity between profits reported by MNCs and domestic firms in the UK using micro-level data, while Fuest, Greil, Hugger and Neumeier (2022) show similar magnitudes of losses for German firms using country-by-country reporting data. Second, growing empirical work has been focusing on examining the consequences of profit shifting on real firm operations (Becker and Riedel; 2012; Bilicka, Qi and Xing; 2022; Egger and Wamser; 2015; Grubert and Slemrod; 1998; Mintz and Smart; 2004; Suárez Serrato; 2018) and the role that local agents play in facilitating profit shifting (Bustos et al.; 2022). Findings from this literature suggest that some profit-shifting restrictions reduce real business operations of firms in countries that introduce them or increase the demand for tax advisory services to enable firms to get around those restrictions. Further, Bilicka, Devereux and Guçeri (2022) show that profit shifting may reduce the cost of investment in productive assets and quantify the resulting trade-off between investment and tax revenue. On the macro level, these real consequences have been shown to affect the estimates of GDP and productivity. Guvenen et al. (2022) find that profit shifting reduces US GDP and productivity estimates in the official statistics and Coppola et al. (2021) find that offshore issuance reduces the scale of portfolio investment from developed countries to emerging market companies. However, none of these studies discuss the consequences of profit shifting on tax revenue structure.

2 Conceptual framework

How do we expect changes in municipal trade tax rates levied on corporate profits and profit shifting to impact tax revenue structure of affected municipalities? In this section, we present three building blocks that connect tax rate changes to firm-level profit shifting responses, municipal trade tax revenues and broader fiscal consequences.

Hypothesis 1 (Profit shifting) A tax rate increase will reduce the amount of profits reported by a subsidiary of an aggressive MNC by more than those reported by a subsidiary of a non-aggressive MNC.

We refer to profit shifting as a practice of MNCs to move profits away from high-tax jurisdictions to low-tax jurisdictions, mostly towards tax havens. Consequently, profits reported by an MNC in a jurisdiction i ($\pi_{corp,i}$) can be expressed as the difference between the “real unobserved profits” (π_i) and profits shifted from the jurisdiction i into tax havens ($\pi_{sh,i}$)

$$\pi_{corp,i} = \pi_i - \pi_{sh,i} \tag{1}$$

Empirical evidence, starting with [Hines and Rice \(1994\)](#), shows that the higher the corporate income tax rate ($\tau_{corp,i}$; or its difference to the tax rate in low-tax jurisdictions where MNC operates), the higher the amount of profit shifting ($\pi_{sh,i}$) and, consequently, the lower the reported profits. This relationship between corporate tax rates and profit shifting is likely to be stronger for more tax aggressive MNCs, such as those which, for example, have ownership links to tax havens, as this indicates an opportunity and ability to engage in profit shifting (e.g. [Gumpert et al.; 2016](#)).

Since a large body of empirical evidence supports this hypothesis (see reviews by, e.g., [Beer et al.; 2020](#); [Riedel; 2018](#)), we merely confirm these findings in the context of firms located in German municipalities between 2008-2019 and report the results using firm-level data in [Appendix C](#). We summarize our findings in [Table C1](#) and in [Figure C1](#), where we show a decline in reported profitability, effective tax rates, and the logarithm of tax paid for subsidiaries of more aggressive MNCs after a tax rate increase in a given municipality. We define a more aggressive MNC as one that has a tax haven subsidiary in its ownership structure. We also show no significant effects on real firm-level operations. In what follows, we focus our analysis on testing the implications of tax rate changes on municipal tax revenue structure, rather than firm-level outcomes.

Hypothesis 2 (Laffer curve) Following a trade tax rate increase, municipalities with higher exposure to aggressive MNCs experience a significant decline in trade tax revenues.

When MNCs shift profits from a municipality, the municipal trade tax revenues are unambiguously negatively affected. The existing literature attempts to quantify the magnitude of the corporate tax revenue lost due to profit shifting. Although no definitive estimate exists, most studies point to a range of tens to two hundreds of billions of US dollars lost annually (e.g., [Bilicka; 2019](#); [Tørsløv et al.; 2023](#); [Fuest, Greil, Hugger and Neumeier; 2022](#); [Garcia-Bernardo and Janský; 2024](#)). The consequences of profit shifting for corporate income tax revenue are also substantial for Germany specifically (e.g., [Fuest, Hugger and Neumeier 2022](#);

Godar 2021; Weichenrieder 2009).

When combined with a trade tax rate increase, the effect of profit shifting on trade tax revenues is ambiguous. In principle, an increase in trade tax rate should increase trade tax revenues, but in the presence of profit shifting this effect could be reduced or even reversed. As such, which effect dominates is an empirical question. If the profit shifting effect dominates, the potential reduction in trade tax revenue in response to trade tax rate increase would also be consistent with the Laffer curve, if we believe that municipalities that are more exposed to profit shifting are on the downward-sloping side of the Laffer curve.

Hypothesis 3 (Fiscal consequences) Following a trade tax rate increase, municipalities with high exposure to aggressive MNCs try to compensate for the lost trade tax revenue with property tax rate and revenue increases.

Following a revenue loss due to profit shifting, do municipal governments actively try to compensate for the lost corporate tax revenues with other tax instruments to increase tax revenues collected from other sources? The existing literature provides some relevant findings. For example, Slemrod and Wilson (2009) present a model in which governments of non-haven countries attempt to limit the transfer of tax revenue from capital taxation to parasitic tax havens. This implies that in the presence of corporate tax revenue losses induced by profit shifting, governments may reduce their overall levels of public expenditures or may rely more heavily on the taxation of labour rather than capital. The authors also show that such increased taxation of labour creates an additional source of deadweight loss and is thus welfare decreasing. Further, in their model Álvarez-Martínez et al. (2021) estimate the scale of profit shifting by assuming that government revenues remain constant. Specifically, any decrease in the corporate tax revenues due to profit shifting leads to an increase in consumption taxes (i.e., value-added tax rates) which is welfare decreasing.

Consequently, in our context, where municipalities can set property tax rates, either those rates will increase, or if no changes to property tax rates occur, the overall tax revenue may decline. For a municipality that wants to keep their budget balanced, this must mean that either they reduce their expenditures or increase government deficits and borrow. While countries have multiple tax rates and tax bases available to them as instruments, at the municipal level in Germany, it is possible that having only one alternative tax instrument may not be sufficient enough and municipalities may lose overall tax revenue when exposed to profit shifting even if they change property tax rates. We test these hypotheses empirically.

3 German municipal context and data

To establish the causal relationship between profit shifting and tax revenue structure, we use municipal-level data on tax rates and tax revenues in Germany combined with firm-level information. Our identification strategy relies on the municipal variation in trade tax rates over time and the presence of subsidiaries of aggressive multinationals across municipalities.

3.1 Institutional context

Tax revenue in Germany is collected at the federal, state, and municipal level. Each governmental unit has control over different types of taxes: the federal government has exclusive power over customs duties and fiscal monopolies; income tax and corporation tax revenues are shared by state and the federal government; 75% of VAT is redistributed across states (European Committee of the Regions; 2022). Municipalities collect trade tax and property tax revenues and get a share of income tax and corporate tax revenues from the federal government (Deloitte; 2022). With over 11,000 municipalities and 16 states, the share of tax revenue collected at the municipal level is 15%, at the state level (Länder) it is 43%, at the federal level it is 39%, and EU contributions form the remaining 4%. Since in this paper, we consider the effects of municipal tax rate changes on local tax revenue structure, we describe how the tax revenue collection at the municipal level is organised in detail.

Municipalities have discretion over two major sources of their tax revenues: trade tax and property tax. 38% of their revenues comes from trade tax and 14% comes from property tax. Other municipal taxes such as a tax on dog ownership are negligible (€1 billion, 1%) and the rest of their revenue comes from federal and state tax apportionment. Specifically, municipalities get a share of wage and assessed income tax and final withholding tax (€41 billion, 38%) and a share of value-added tax (€9 billion, 8%). In return, municipalities have to apportion a share of their trade tax revenue to state and federal government; in 2020, they apportioned around 10%: €4 billion out of total €41 billion trade tax revenue.

Trade tax (Gewerbesteuer) is a tax on companies' profits and the tax rate is a combination of a base rate of 3.5%, uniform across Germany, and a municipal multiplier (Hebesatz), determined by each municipality, applicable according to where the companies' permanent establishments are located. Municipalities vote on the next year's multiplier annually and when changed, the multiplier is valid for at least one full budget year. There is no ceiling on the multiplier, but a floor was introduced in 2004, before our data sample starts.⁶ The

⁶Foremny and Riedel (2014) observe a political cycle in tax setting as the growth in the multiplier is

tax rate is determined with the multiplier (m_i) in the following way: $t_i = \frac{m_i \times 0.035}{100 + (m_i \times 0.035)}$. In 2019, the last year in our sample, the effective trade tax rate varied between 6.5% ($m_i = 200$) and 17.3% ($m_i = 600$), with an average of 11.3%. Important for us, municipalities control the multiplier, but not the tax base, which is slightly different than for corporate income tax purposes and includes operating profits earned within the boundaries of a municipality. Further, if a firm has multiple establishments across municipalities, the taxable profits are allocated across firm locations according to each municipality’s wage bill share.⁷ In addition to trade tax collected by municipalities, corporate profits are taxed by the federal government at a uniform rate of 15.825% (including a solidarity surcharge).

Property tax (Grundsteuer) is a tax on the assessed value of property. There are two types of property taxes in Germany, A and B. Property tax A is levied on the value of property used for agriculture and forestry and property tax B is levied on the value of other developed and constructible land, such as that for commercial and residential property. The tax rate is a combination of a base rate (depends on the type of property, but is uniform across Germany and mostly 0.35%) and the local multiplier, determined by each municipality. Similar to trade tax, the municipal council makes decisions about the local multiplier and can do so every year. Further, all the other characteristics and regulations of the property tax are set at the national level and, hence, are uniform across the municipalities.⁸ Similarly, the value of the property is assessed by the state tax offices and not by the municipality; also this assessment is done when the property is built and remains unchanged over time (Löffler and Siegloch; 2021). The average effective property tax rate A was 11.9% and the average property tax rate B was 13.3% in 2019. The property tax rate B generally tends to be higher than that for property type A. Unless specifically referred to, we calculate the average of the two property tax rates and consider the change in property tax rate as either a change in property rate A, or B, or both.

significantly reduced in the election year and the year prior to the election, while it significantly increases in the year after the election. Also for Germany, Riedel and Simmler (2021) find that municipalities that host large firms tend to have lower trade tax rates.

⁷Note that trade tax is levied not only on corporations but also on the non-incorporated sector such as sole proprietorships and partnerships. Our firm-level data only includes corporations, so we will focus on those in the remainder of the paper.

⁸The 2019 reform that gave more flexibility to states in designing the tax starting from 2022 does not influence the period covered by our analysis.

3.2 Data and data construction

Municipal-level data Germany provides a good laboratory to study the relationship between profit shifting and tax revenue structure due to the availability of high-quality municipal- and firm-level data. Detailed information on tax structure is available from the German Office of Statistics for each of the 11,000 municipalities and each of them chooses its own rate of trade tax and property tax. This level of local autonomy is rare. The municipal level data includes information on total tax revenue, which includes the amounts apportioned to and from federal and state governments, trade tax revenue, and property tax revenue. We use this data to construct a share of trade tax and property tax in total tax revenue as well as a logarithm of both trade and property tax revenue. We also include results using overall tax revenues and property tax rate as outcome variables. Given that we rely on the variation in trade tax rates to identify the relationship between tax revenue structure and profit shifting, we consider trade tax rates as an outcome variable to allow us to calculate the magnitude of elasticities only. We have data at the municipal level available between 2008 and 2019.

Firm-level data The firm-level data comes from the Bureau van Dijk Orbis dataset and includes the location of over 3.9 million German firms. This is line with 4 million business taxpayers that the German Statistical office reports in 2018.⁹ We have a detailed firm address, postcode, and city for each of those firms. We match each of those firm addresses to the municipal location using GIS software and we find a match for 97% of our firm-level observations.¹⁰ We use Orbis ownership data from 2019 to identify firms into domestic standalones, domestic groups, foreign multinationals, and domestic multinationals. We do not utilize the historical ownership data, as the coverage is limited relative to the static data and biased towards larger, multinational firms. Note that this requires us to assume that ownership did not change during the analysed period; 2008—2019. This is a plausible assumption used in other papers in this literature, e.g. [Bilicka \(2019\)](#), but it does constitute a limitation of this study.

We define foreign multinationals as those firms with headquarters outside of Germany and domestic multinationals as firms that are headquartered in Germany but have at least one foreign affiliate that they own by more than 50%. This assumption ensures that we only include subsidiaries that are directly controlled by MNCs and are more likely to be used by them for profit-shifting purposes. In our main analysis, we consider subsidiaries of

⁹https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Government/Taxes/Business-Tax/_node.html

¹⁰98% of the 117,000 firms for which we do not find a match are mostly domestic standalone with no ownership or financial information in Orbis.

both domestic and foreign multinationals together and show results separately in section 5.5. Our sample includes 22,674 subsidiaries of foreign MNCs and 50,543 subsidiaries of domestic MNCs. Given that the German statistical office reports to have 26,951 CFCs (controlled foreign companies) which employ over 3.8 million people in Germany in 2019, we cover over 84% of the CFCs and 44% of the people that they employ.¹¹ Using the ownership structure of firms, we define aggressive multinationals, as those that have at least one affiliate in a tax haven (Bilicka and Scur; 2021; Gumpert et al.; 2016; Hines and Rice; 1994).¹²

We identify over 8,000 affiliates that belong to more aggressive MNCs of which 835 belong to foreign MNCs and the remainder to domestic MNCs. We then collect unconsolidated balance sheet information for all firms in Germany (when available), which allows us to have total assets, fixed assets, employment, profits, and other variables at the affiliate level.

Unit of analysis We conduct our analysis at the municipality-year level. As such, we collapse the firm-level data by the municipality in which these firms are located. This results in 111,534 observations across 9,317 municipalities for the period 2008—2019. The identifying variation we explore in this paper is the presence of affiliates that belong to more tax-aggressive multinationals across German municipalities. For that purpose, we consider both the count of these affiliates and their share in all firms in each municipality. We also use the share of real business operations to define municipalities more exposed to aggressive MNCs. In placebo tests, we use the count and share of all multinational affiliates. On average, a municipality has 486 firms with 2 domestic MNC affiliates and 0.5 foreign affiliates. 1 of those 2.5 affiliates is aggressive. As such, the share of MNCs in each municipality firm count is, on average, 0.2%, with a large variation ranging from municipalities that have no MNC presence to those that have over 3.5% of their firms belonging to multinationals. We provide descriptive statistics on these municipalities in Table B1 and information outlining the municipal variation in trade tax rates and exposure to aggressive MNCs in Appendix B.

¹¹For detailed statistics see https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Economic-Sectors-Enterprises/Enterprises/Foreign-controlled-enterprises/_node.html#265834. Also note that this is consistent with relatively incomplete reporting of financial information by Orbis, which we directly show in Table B2.

¹²As Tørsløv et al. (2023) point out Orbis data has poor coverage for financial information in tax havens, but firms do report a presence in tax havens and this is the only information we require here. Bilicka and Scur (2021) use this same nomenclature to define more plausibly tax-aggressive firms. For a list of tax haven subsidiaries that belong to MNCs with presence in Germany, as reported by Orbis, see Table C2 in the Appendix.

4 Identification strategy

Our identification strategy uses increases in trade tax rates at the municipal level across the years. As such, we identify municipalities that increased their trade tax rates and use these changes to show the effect of tax rate increases on tax revenue structure for municipalities with different exposures to aggressive MNCs.¹³ We stack each of these tax rate increases to occur at time $t=0$. In that, we use a stacked event study framework that follows [Fuest et al. \(2018\)](#), who look at municipal trade tax rate changes and their effect on wages. In our data, we identify 9,606 events when the municipality increased the trade tax rate. This means that around 5,800 municipalities experienced at least 1 trade tax rate increase and these form our treatment group. Within that treatment group, 61% of municipalities increased their trade tax rate once during the sample period, 24% twice, and the remainder increased these rates multiple times. 3,370 municipalities never experienced a trade tax rate increase and they form the control group. In the main analysis, we limit the treatment sample to municipalities that only experienced one tax rate increase to estimate the magnitude of the revenue effect related to a single tax rate change.¹⁴

To compare the effects of tax rate increases between municipalities that are more or less exposed to aggressive MNCs, we use two exposure variables. First, we convert the continuous variable on the share of affiliates that belong to aggressive MNCs to a binary variable that splits the share according to a median across municipalities. Second, we use the count of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs. There are two identifying assumptions underlying our analysis. First, the location of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs is not correlated with tax rate changes or levels in the municipalities that they reside in. To evaluate the plausibility of this assumption, we calculate the correlation between the share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs in all firms in each municipality and (1) trade tax rates, (2) the number of trade tax rate changes, and (3) the size of the trade tax rate changes. In each of the three cases we find no significant correlation with the share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs.¹⁵ Second, treated municipalities did not evolve differentially from the control group before the reform. To test the plausibility of this assumption and to provide a dynamic evolution of the effects, we estimate the following event study model:

¹³The majority of municipal rate changes are trade tax rate increases. In fact, only 6% of trade tax rate changes in our sample are tax decreases.

¹⁴In section 5.5 we show that our results remain unchanged when we use the full set of tax rate increases.

¹⁵The correlations are respectively 0.003 (st. error 0.79), -.004 (st error 0.08) and -0.012 (st error 0.26).

$$T_{it} = \alpha + \sum_{\kappa=\underline{\kappa}}^{\bar{\kappa}} \delta_t D_{it} + \sum_{\kappa=\underline{\kappa}}^{\bar{\kappa}} \beta_t (D_{it} \times hMNC_i) + \sigma_1 X'_{it} + \eta_i + \phi_j t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where T_{it} is a share of tax revenues coming from corporations, property taxes, the log of tax revenues coming from each source, and property tax rates. D_{it} is a binned treatment adoption indicator that we define following (McCrory; 2007; Schmidheiny and Siegloch; 2023) as:

$$D_{it} = \begin{cases} \mathbb{1}[t \leq E_i + \kappa] & \text{if } \kappa = \underline{\kappa} \\ \mathbb{1}[t = E_i + \kappa] & \text{if } \underline{\kappa} < \kappa < \bar{\kappa} \\ \mathbb{1}[t \geq E_i + \kappa] & \text{if } \kappa = \bar{\kappa} \end{cases}$$

where $\mathbb{1}$ is a series of year dummies that equal one when the tax reform was κ years away with the dummy variable corresponding to $\kappa = -1$ as the omitted category relative to which all coefficient estimates are normalized. E_i is the year of the trade tax rate increase in each municipality. $\underline{\kappa}=-3$ and $\bar{\kappa}=3$ indicating that we bin event dummies at $t = -3$ and $t = 3$ such that the end dummies include any years beyond the window. Note that these dummies are equal to zero for the municipalities where no trade tax rate changes occur, i.e. for our control group. $hMNC_i$ is a dummy equal to 1 when the share of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs in a given municipality is larger than the median or it is a count of the number of those subsidiaries. X_{it} includes municipal and property tax rates, the number of firms in each municipality, and the population. η_i are municipality fixed effects and $\phi_j t$ are state times year fixed effects. The inclusion of state times year fixed effects controls for the fact that there are differences in tax rates in levels and in changes, and fiscal equalisation rules across states. We cluster standard errors at the municipal level in each estimation. The coefficients of interest are the β_t : they estimate the differences in the outcome variables between municipalities with high and low exposure to aggressive MNCs, κ years before or after the reform, relative to the control group of municipalities that did not change their trade tax rate at all.

Our identification strategy relies on using the traditional two-way fixed effects approach. However, this approach may raise concerns due to the staggered and heterogeneous nature of reform implementation across municipalities and years. There is a possibility that the estimated effects may be contaminated when “already-treated” observations are used as a control group, as they introduce negative weights into the regression analysis. To address

these concerns, we adopt three strategies. First, in our baseline regressions, we only use municipalities that experienced one tax rate increase as our treated group and municipalities that experienced no tax rate increases or decreases as our control group. As such, we exclude municipalities that changed their tax rates multiple times and municipalities that reduced their rate. This strategy limits the exposure to the staggered implementation, as we do not use the already treated municipalities as a control group. Second, when we include the full sample of tax rate increases, we decompose our estimator into its sources of variation, showing that our estimates rely predominantly on the comparison of “treated” with “never-treated” groups (Goodman-Bacon; 2021). Third, we use alternative estimators to correct for the remaining concerns about the heterogeneous treatment effects in a staggered difference-in-differences framework, including those provided by De Chaisemartin and d’Haultfoeuille (2020), Sun and Abraham (2021), and Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021), when estimating the event study models with two-way fixed effects.

5 Baseline estimates

We start by reporting simple difference-in-differences coefficient estimates from a model that underlines the event studies described above. As such, we estimate the following simple equation:

$$T_{it} = post_t \times hMNC_i + \sigma_1 X'_{it} + \eta_i + \delta_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

where $post_t$ is a dummy equal to 1 in all years after the trade tax rate increase, and zero otherwise. Note that the post dummy is also equal to zero for all the municipalities that did not change their trade tax rate during the sample period. All other variables are defined above. We summarise results from this baseline estimation in Table 1 using the share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs in all firms in the municipality as an interaction in Panel A and the number of those subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs in Panel B. We start with describing results in Panel A. On average, in municipalities with *low* exposure to aggressive MNCs, the increase in trade tax rate of 4.4% (column 1 coefficient on $post=1$) leads to a 3.1% increase in trade tax revenue (column 3) and a 0.9% increase in total tax revenue relative to the control group.

However, municipalities with more exposure to aggressive MNCs significantly reduce the level and the share of tax revenue they derive from trade taxes, following a trade tax rate increase. Specifically, results from column (3) indicate that municipalities with a high share

of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs see a reduction in trade tax revenues of about 3.1% ($=3.1-6.2$) relative to the control group, despite the fact that the average tax rate in those municipalities increases by a smaller magnitude, 4% ($=4.4-0.4$), than in the municipalities with lower exposure to aggressive MNCs. The shares result from column (4) suggests that these municipalities also have a 1.4% ($=0.6-2$) lower share of trade tax revenue in all revenues relative to the control group. Consequently, this means that they lose about 1.2% ($=0.9-2.1$) of total tax revenues following the tax rate increase (column 5).¹⁶

Further, we find that changes in trade tax rates are often accompanied by changes in property tax rates of similar magnitudes. Specifically, following a trade tax rate increase of 4.4% (column 1), the property tax rates increase by an average of 3.9% (column 2) across all municipalities.¹⁷ This relationship is no different between those municipalities that are more or less exposed to aggressive MNCs. This suggests that municipalities that increase the trade tax rates may be using property tax rates as an instrument to increase their total tax revenues as well. However, despite the property tax rate increases, we find no evidence of changes in property tax revenues. The increase in the share of property tax revenues in all tax revenue for municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs documented in column (7) is not large enough to prevent the overall loss of municipal tax revenue, as documented in column (5). One way to interpret these results is that property tax is not a strong enough instrument to offset changes in trade tax revenue.

We find very similar results in Panel B, using the number of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs, instead of shares of subsidiaries. An advantage of this estimation is that the coefficients are easy to interpret. For example, results from column 3 suggest that an additional subsidiary that belongs to an aggressive MNC in a municipality would reduce the trade tax revenue following a tax rate increase by 0.35% relative to a municipality that did not have any such subsidiaries. The average number of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs is 0.9, but 83.6% of municipalities do not have any. Amongst those that have at least 1 such subsidiary, the average is 5.5 subsidiaries. As such, for an average municipality that is exposed to aggressive MNCs, the loss in trade tax revenue is about 1.925% relative to an average municipality that is not exposed to any aggressive MNCs.

To show the evolution of tax revenue structure around the tax rate increase, we plot

¹⁶All these magnitudes are computed by adding up coefficients on post and post \times high share.

¹⁷Note that the magnitude of these trade tax rate increases is the same between more or less indebted municipalities, but the property tax rate only increases in more indebted municipalities. This suggests that some of this effect may be driven by high fiscal pressure. However, we should interpret these results with caution, since we observe debt only for a small sub-sample of municipalities for which we have tax revenue data.

the event study coefficients for high and low exposure municipalities relative to the control group separately in Figure 1. We mark high exposure municipalities with empty diamonds and blue confidence intervals and low exposure municipalities with filled circles and red confidence intervals. In this figure, we use the above and below median shares of subsidiaries that belong to more aggressive MNCs as an exposure variable. As such, these results are analogous to Panel A from Table 1. In Panel (a), we start by showing the evolution of tax rate changes where the magnitudes correspond to those in column (1), Panel A in Table 1. Further, these plots suggest that the trade tax rate changes we consider are, by construction, highly persistent.

Panels (b) and (c) demonstrate a large decline in trade tax revenues and total tax revenues at the time of the tax rate increase for high exposure municipalities and an increase in those revenues for low exposure municipalities. Panel (d) shows the evolution of the share of trade tax revenues in total tax revenue across years in our sample. We find that following a trade tax rate increase there is a steady decline in the share of trade tax revenues in more exposed municipalities relative to the control group. Before the trade tax rate increase, there is no difference in the evolution of the trade tax revenue levels and shares for municipalities with high exposure to aggressive MNCs relative to the control group. At the same time, we find that in the less exposed municipalities the level and the share of trade tax revenue was higher before the tax rate reform and continues to be higher after relative to the control group.

We show that these effects are not symmetric. In Figure A1 we plot the event study coefficients from regressions where we consider municipalities in which the trade tax rate decreased relative to those where the trade tax rate did not change at all, analogous to Figure 1. While we find that the magnitude of the tax rate decline is similar to that of the tax increase (panel a), we find no significant effects for either shares or levels of trade tax revenues or total tax revenues for either the low or high exposure municipalities. There are two potential explanations for this finding. First, the number of tax rate decreases is very small relative to tax rate increases, hence the sample size is smaller and could explain insignificant effects. Second, when a trade tax rate declines, an aggressive MNC is unlikely to bring profits back to Germany, as Germany is generally considered a relatively high-tax rate country. As such, these results support the conceptual framework in which MNCs move profits out of municipalities that increase their trade tax rates but do not move them back when the trade tax rate declines.

5.1 Elasticity calculations

We use our estimates to calculate the elasticity of the trade tax revenues response with respect to the one-minus-the-trade-tax-rate for the municipalities with low and high exposure to more aggressive MNCs. For that, we use the results from columns 1 and 3 in Panel A of Table 1. We use the standard elasticity formula: $elasticity_{\tau rev} = \Delta Y_i / [(\tau_{new} - \tau_{old}) / (1 - \tau_{old})]$, where ΔY_i is a change in trade tax revenue in response to the tax increase, τ_{new} is the average tax rate after the tax rate increase and τ_{old} is the previous tax rate. Given the evidence from Figure 1, we can assume that $(\tau_{new} - \tau_{old}) = 4.4\%$ for municipalities with low exposure to aggressive MNCs, while the change in tax rate is 4% for those with high exposure. We can also assume that τ_{old} is zero in both cases, as this is what the pre-trends imply. As such, $elasticity_{\tau rev} = \Delta Y_i / (4.4\%)$ in case of low exposure municipalities and $elasticity_{\tau rev} = \Delta Y_i / (4\%)$ in case of higher exposure ones.

Consequently, with the average change in trade tax revenue of 3.1% (column 3), we obtain an elasticity of 0.705 for low-exposure municipalities. With the average change in trade tax revenue of -3.1% for high-exposure municipalities, we obtain an elasticity of -0.775. The estimate in the case of low-exposure municipalities is broadly similar in magnitude to comparable elasticities by [Devereux et al. \(2014\)](#), who exploit UK tax returns data and two kinks in the tax schedule to estimate it to be 0.13 and 0.17 for one kink and 0.53 and 0.56 for another kink. The effect of trade tax rate increase on trade tax revenues is significant in the case of high-exposure municipalities and its magnitude of -0.775 is consistent with profit shifting elasticities such as those in the meta-analysis by [Beer et al.; 2020](#), who estimate the elasticity to be -1.0 for their whole sample and -1.5 for the most recent years.

5.2 Potential mechanisms

Cross-municipality vs cross-border spillovers There are two potential reasons why the level and share of trade tax revenues at the municipal level may decline as a result of trade tax rate increases. First, multinationals may choose to move profits away from municipalities that levy larger taxes on them. In principle, they can move these profits either to other municipalities in Germany that have lower tax rates or move them abroad to their other affiliates in low-tax countries. Since within Germany, the tax liability is apportioned according to the share of wages across municipalities, a priori we do not expect moving profits across municipalities to play a large role in our setting. While, [Riedel \(2010\)](#) shows that firms used to do that before 2008, we find no significant evidence for cross-municipality spillovers after 2008. We discuss our evidence in detail in Section 6. However, given that profits are

mobile across country borders, an increase in trade tax rate can potentially be immediately reflected in corporate profits and consequently in municipal tax revenues, if MNCs move profits abroad. This mechanism is consistent with the profit-shifting explanation that we propose in the paper.

Cross-municipality and cross-border shifting may have opposite effects on tax base of our control group municipalities. If firms move profits across municipalities in response to a tax rate increase, we would observe an increase in tax revenues in the control municipality. Cross-border shifting in the presence of formula apportionment means that the control municipalities could also see a decrease in tax revenues, as a smaller tax base will be apportioned. It is crucial to rule these spillovers out, as they pose a threat to our identification strategy violating the difference-in-differences assumption. We rule the cross-municipality spillovers by including the average neighbouring municipalities trade tax rate as an explanatory variable in our regressions and showing that its effect is not statistically significant, as we discuss in Section 6. While we cannot estimate the effect of the trade tax rate changes on the control group directly, we can trace the evolution of the control group municipalities' revenues in response to changes in the neighbouring trade tax rates. We do that in Figure A3 in which we see no significant changes in the control group revenues around the change in their neighbouring trade tax rate. Since the two types of spillovers counteract each other, it is possible that they both can be at play. However, since they jointly do not seem to affect the evolution of our control group, they do not pose a threat to our identification strategy.

Reallocation of operations The second possibility is that a trade tax rate increase results in the reallocation of firms' or business operations away from municipalities that enact those tax rate hikes. To the extent that incentives for the reallocation of real operations should not differ between more and less aggressive MNCs, we provide placebo tests using the share of all MNCs in each municipality to show no tax revenue effects of trade tax rate hikes in municipalities simply more exposed to MNCs.

However, a possibility exists that profit shifting may be accompanied by reallocation of real operations, as in Bilicka, Qi and Xing (2022). In that case, municipalities more exposed to aggressive MNCs may be more prone to real business operations reallocation. To test whether that occurs in our sample, we consider aggregated firm-level employment, total assets, and turnover, as well as municipal-level wage and income taxes as outcome variables using the specification outlined in equation (2). We plot the results in Figure 2 which follows the exposure from Figure 1.¹⁸ We do not find any meaningful changes in

¹⁸We report the aggregated post coefficients in Table A2 in the Appendix, following the format of results

employment, assets or turnover around the time of the trade tax rate increase in either low or high exposure municipalities. We also find no effect of the tax rate increase on municipal wage or income tax revenues, which suggests that no meaningful reallocation of employees for formula apportionment purposes occurs either. This lack of significant changes in real business operations suggests that we can rule out real responses where firms move their real business operations out of Germany in response to local business tax rate increases. This is similar to what [Lichter et al. \(2021\)](#) find. As such, our results support the main mechanism we propose to be at play — profit shifting.

6 Robustness tests

Accounting for firm size and operations In our baseline estimates, we use the number of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive multinationals to calculate the exposure to more aggressive MNCs. In principle, the more assets, profits, turnover, or employment these MNCs have in each municipality, the larger the exposure and the potential responses to trade tax rate increases. Orbis data collects information on these real business operations, but the data has a much smaller coverage. In [Table B2](#) in the Appendix we summarise the municipal-level coverage for financial information in Orbis for all firms (Panel A) and multinational firms (Panel B). On average, the coverage is quite poor, with about 2.2% of firms reporting employment and profits. Multinationals have better coverage with over 30% of their subsidiaries having information on employment, turnover, and profits.

In [Table 2](#) we use the real business operation weights and consider the effects of a trade tax rate increase on the logarithm of trade tax revenues (Panel A), the share of trade tax revenues in all tax revenues (Panel B), and the logarithm of total tax revenues (Panel C). As such, these results are comparable to those from columns 3, 4, and 5 from [Table 1](#), respectively. Here, instead of dummies for high and low exposure to aggressive MNCs, we use real business operation shares to proxy for municipal exposure to more aggressive MNCs. Specifically, we use the share of assets, the share of employment, the share of turnover, and the share of profits respectively. The caveat with these results is that we have a much smaller coverage of real business operations that is highly skewed towards MNCs. Nevertheless, we find results consistent with our baseline estimates. The trade tax revenue falls after a tax rate increase in municipalities with a higher share of business operations owned by subsidiaries that belong to more aggressive MNCs, relative to those with no such subsidiaries. This result

presented in [Table 1](#).

is statistically significant and persistent across all measures of business operations: assets, employment, turnover, and profits. We also continue to find that in municipalities that are not exposed to aggressive MNCs at all, the increase in trade tax rate results in an increase in trade tax and overall tax revenue.

The magnitude of the effect estimated in column (2) in Panel (A), for example, suggests that if subsidiaries belonging to aggressive MNCs employ 11% of people in a given municipality, an increase in the trade tax rate would bring no additional trade tax revenues. If these subsidiaries employ more than 11% of people, there will be a decline in trade tax revenue. Most municipalities, 82.6%, do not report any employees that can be attributed to aggressive MNCs (see Figure B2). However, amongst those that do, the average amount of people employed by subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs is 17.8%. Hence, similar to baseline results, an average municipality that is more exposed to aggressive MNCs loses trade tax revenues following a trade tax rate increase.

Placebo with all MNCs One potential concern with our identification strategy could be that what we pick up is the presence of subsidiaries that belong to MNCs in each municipality more generally, rather than the presence of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs. This could mean that our result may be related to competition between domestic and multinational firms instead. To attenuate this concern in Table A1 we show results using a share of subsidiaries that belong to MNCs in Panel A and the count of these subsidiaries in Panel B following the exposition from Table 1. We find no systematic statistically significant evidence for a decline in trade tax or total tax revenue in municipalities with a higher share (or higher number) of subsidiaries that belong to any MNCs.

We then turn to additional tests of the robustness of our baseline findings. We summarise our results in Figure 3 in which we show the interaction coefficients between a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs and $\text{post}=1$ dummies only, omitting $\text{post}=1$ dummy for the clarity of exposition. We present four sets of figures, each looking at a different outcome variable: the logarithm of trade tax revenues (panel a), the logarithm of property tax revenues (panel b), the share of trade tax revenues in total tax revenues (panel c), and the logarithm of total tax revenues (panel d). Within each figure we show the robustness of the baseline result by comparing the interaction coefficient, labeled baseline and represented by a black diamond, using various sample cuts and variable definitions. First, we consider the effect of using all tax rate increases and consequently all municipalities in our treatment group (black squares). The results remain virtually unchanged across all outcome variables.

Municipality size differences Second, we weigh the results using population (black triangles). A potential concern could be that our results are picking up effects coming from small municipalities, where multinationals contribute a larger share to total corporate tax revenues. In that case, if a subsidiary of an aggressive MNC shifts profits, it will have a large effect on revenues. This could bias the size of the estimates coefficients upwards. We attenuate this concern by showing that the results weighted by population are very similar in magnitude to the baseline across our main outcome variables of interest. Further, we separately show the results for small and large municipalities in Table A4 in the Appendix where the effects are not statistically significantly different between the two sub-samples, though the effects for small municipalities are much more heterogeneous.

Cross-municipality spillovers Third, we include as control variables the average of the five neighbouring trade and property tax rates. There are two reasons why we may want to include this control. First, one may be concerned that municipalities compete over firm presence and tax revenues using tax rates and this may affect smaller municipalities, in particular, Buettner (2003). If this was driving our results, we would expect that controlling for the neighbouring tax rates would reduce the magnitude of the coefficient on the main interaction effect of interest. Instead, we find coefficient magnitudes that are quite similar (coefficients marked by crosses), though with higher standard errors that may suggest some heterogeneity across municipalities.¹⁹

Additionally, in columns 5 and 6 in Table A2 in the Appendix, we look directly at the average of the neighbouring trade and property tax rates as outcome variables following a trade tax rate increase in a given municipality. We find a small increase in the average trade tax rate of neighbouring municipalities following a trade tax rate increase in municipalities with *both* low and high exposure to aggressive MNCs. In sum, these results suggest that tax competition may occur locally, but does not affect the magnitude of our baseline estimates since we rely on the variation between municipalities with high and low exposure to aggressive MNCs.

Second, Riedel (2010) shows that despite the formula apportionment regime, profit shifting occurs at the municipal level in Germany. If firms shift profits to other municipalities, we would expect that an increase in neighbouring trade tax rate would increase trade tax rev-

¹⁹Note that the sample size here is smaller since we compute the average of 5 neighbouring municipalities and those without 5 neighbours drop out of the sample. We test the robustness of this using the average trade and property tax rates of 3 and 4 neighbouring municipalities and the results remain unchanged. We do not report these coefficients.

venues of the municipality itself. This could render the municipalities with no trade tax rate changes an inappropriate control group in our setting. We examine this in detail by looking at the coefficient on the average of trade tax rate of neighbouring municipalities directly. We find it is positive, though not significant in any of our specifications. While our results are qualitatively consistent with evidence from [Riedel \(2010\)](#), it appears that in recent years profit shifting between municipalities may be a less important channel than it was before 2008. Further, one may still be concerned that firms could move profits to municipalities that are not necessarily neighbouring ones. To answer this concern, we calculate the average trade tax rate for all municipalities in Germany, excluding the affected one and include that average as a control variable. This does not affect the magnitudes of our baseline estimates and the coefficient itself is also never statistically significant and very small in magnitude.

The role of apportionment Fourth, we consider the effect that apportionment can have on our baseline estimates. Specifically, we subtract apportionment from trade tax revenues in Panel a.²⁰ Because federal and state governments may apportion some of their revenues to municipalities that see a reduction in their own tax revenues, including apportionment may reduce the magnitude of the trade tax revenue estimates. However, since municipalities also apportion some of their revenues back to state and federal governments, this may attenuate the effect. We show that excluding apportionment from trade tax revenues does not change the magnitude of the estimate relative to the baseline (marked by a plus in panel a). Hence, apportionment does not play a large role in our setting.

Alternative aggressiveness proxy Fifth, we show that our results are robust to using an alternative measure of aggressiveness. One could plausibly argue that the presence of a tax haven in the ownership structure could indicate other motives beyond profit shifting, such as desire to avoid regulation or capital controls. Further, MNCs without tax haven presence may also be aggressive profit shifters, which would mean we misclassify firms. To attenuate these concerns, we construct an alternative proxy. Using the firm-level data from Orbis we estimate the traditional profit shifting elasticities using ROA (returns on assets) as an outcome variable for each of the approximately 21,200 MNCs in our sample. We then split those elasticities into those that are in the bottom 25th percentile of the distribution and are all negative, indicating that the firm is reducing reported profitability in response to tax rate increase, and those in the top 25th percentile of the distribution which are all

²⁰We do that only for panel a, as there is no apportionment for property tax revenue and the one for overall tax revenue is not reported in the data we have.

positive.²¹ We denote firms with negative elasticities as aggressive and calculate the share of MNC subsidiaries that belong to these aggressive firms for each municipality, similar to our baseline. We find results that are both qualitatively and quantitatively similar using this alternative aggressiveness proxy.

Domestic vs foreign MNCs Sixth, we consider the presence of subsidiaries that belong to domestic and foreign MNCs separately, in a spirit similar to [Becker et al. \(2012\)](#). Red diamonds correspond to results for the share of subsidiaries that belong to foreign MNCs, while blue diamonds correspond to those belonging to domestic MNCs. We find no significant effect of the trade tax rate increase on the trade tax revenues of municipalities with a larger share of subsidiaries that belong to domestic or foreign MNCs. Consistent with the results from the placebo test in [Table A1](#), the magnitude of the estimated effect is very small relative to the baseline estimate and not statistically significant. Unlike [Becker et al. \(2012\)](#), we do not find a differential effect of the trade tax rate increases between municipalities differentially exposed to domestic and foreign MNCs.²²

Finally, instead of looking at the share of subsidiaries that belong to more aggressive MNCs and the share of subsidiaries of MNCs separately, we combine the two to consider the share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs in all MNCs' subsidiaries in each municipality. This is a continuous variable and we denote the coefficient estimate by a black circle. Similar to baseline results, the larger the share of aggressive MNCs in all MNCs in each municipality, the lower the potential trade tax revenue, the share of tax revenue coming from trade taxes, and the overall municipal tax revenue.

The staggered nature of the tax rate cuts In [Figure 3](#), we demonstrate that our estimates are robust to including in our sample all municipalities, rather than just those with one tax rate increase. In this subsection, we continue using that extended sample, to show that our results are robust to the new two-way fixed effects literature using the proposed corrections. First, we decompose the overall effect we obtain from our regressions into its sources of variation following [Goodman-Bacon \(2021\)](#). In [Table A3](#) we show that our estimates rely almost exclusively on the comparison of “treated” with “never-treated”

²¹Results using median, which is zero, as a cutoff are also qualitatively similar, but the magnitude of the estimated coefficient is smaller.

²²There are at least two potential explanations for this difference. First, [Becker et al. \(2012\)](#) use a sample that covers a much earlier period 2001 - 2005, before the large corporate tax rate cuts that were enacted in Germany in 2008. Second, their estimates include a host of control variables that we do not include in our baseline estimates.

groups. Hence, the staggered implementation of the reform should not substantially bias our baseline estimates.

What remains, is the concern about the heterogeneous size of the tax rate increases across municipalities. To attenuate concerns about the potential bias this could introduce into our baseline estimates, in Figure A2 we present estimates using corrections for the staggered heterogeneous difference-in-differences estimators, as suggested by Roth et al. (2022). In panel a, we show results using the logarithm of trade tax revenues as an outcome variable, while in panel b, we show results using the logarithm of property tax revenues. Generally, the magnitude of our baseline OLS estimates, which are also plotted alongside the corrections, is similar to that using Sun and Abraham (2021), De Chaisemartin and d’Haultfoeuille (2020), and Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) corrections. The Callaway and Sant’Anna (2021) estimator has larger standard errors, but generates a similar magnitude of the estimated differences between municipalities with high and low exposure to aggressive MNCs. We continue to find a negative effect of the tax rate increase on trade tax revenues, with no effect on property tax revenues.

7 Fiscal consequences

7.1 The role of property tax rates

There are two pieces of evidence we provide to show how municipalities respond to potential changes in tax revenues following trade tax rate increase. First is descriptive. In Table B3, we document that in most cases, 54.2%, municipalities change at least one of the property tax rates *and* the trade tax rates at the same time. When they do that, the increase in the property tax rate is, on average, higher – 0.98 percentage point for property tax rate A and 1.12 for property tax B – than that for the trade tax rate – 0.66 percentage point (Panel A). In 33.6% of cases municipalities change only the property tax rates but not the trade tax rate and in 12.1% they change only the trade tax rate but neither of the property tax rates.

We then compare these descriptives across municipalities that are more (Panel B) or less (Panel C) exposed to aggressive MNCs. We find that municipalities that are more exposed change both property and trade tax rates together in 56.5% of cases while those less exposed in 53.6% of cases. Not only do municipalities with more exposure change these two taxes together more often, but the magnitude of these rate changes is also smaller. Further, the magnitude of trade tax rate changes relative to property tax rate changes is smaller for municipalities more exposed to aggressive MNCs. These descriptives suggest that

municipalities use property tax rates as an instrument when changing their trade tax rates and, likely, given that property tax rate is charged on less mobile capital and smaller tax base, they can, and do, increase that rate more and increase it more frequently than trade tax rates. The role of property tax rate is especially pronounced in municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs.

The second piece of evidence on the role of property tax rates as an instrument to complement trade tax rate changes comes from comparing cases when municipalities increase *only* the trade tax rate and cases when municipalities increase *both* the trade tax rate and at least one of the property tax rates at the same time. We compare estimates from those regressions in Panels A and B of Table 3, respectively. We find that the reduction in *total* tax revenue that we observe in the full sample, is driven entirely by cases where trade tax rates increased on their own without the corresponding increases in either of the property tax rates. In Panel A column (3) the effect of the trade tax rate increase on total tax revenues is positive in municipalities both more and less exposed to aggressive MNCs relative to our control group. In Panel B, we further show that when trade tax rate increases without the corresponding increase in either of the property tax rates, the overall effect on trade tax revenue in municipalities more exposed to aggressive MNCs is larger than when trade tax increases in conjunction with property tax rate increase. Further, in column (3), the overall tax revenue impact of such a change in more exposed municipalities is negative.²³

These results suggest that property tax rates have an integral role as an instrument to prevent revenue loss at the municipal level. While municipalities that are more exposed to aggressive MNCs still lose trade tax revenues following a trade tax rate increase, if they increase either or both of the property rates at the same time, they do not see an overall loss in total tax revenues relative to municipalities that are less exposed to aggressive MNCs.

7.2 Expenditures and debt

Does the reduction in tax revenues that we demonstrate in our analysis affect municipal expenditures and consequently their GDP and debt? We summarise the results from this analysis in Table 4 in which we consider the differential responses of GDP, expenditures, and debt between municipalities that were more or less exposed to aggressive MNCs. In Panel A, in columns 1-3 we use the continuous variable which is the number of subsidiaries

²³While it would be interesting to examine the role of either of the two types of property taxes that German municipalities levy separately, we do not have enough cases of trade tax rate changing with either but not both of these taxes to provide meaningful evidence. As we document in Table B3 trade taxes change together with *both* property tax rates in 82% of all cases when these rates move jointly.

that belong to aggressive MNCs. In columns 4-6, we use the dummy variable equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries belonging to more aggressive MNCs is larger than the median. We find that following a trade tax rate increase, there is a significant reduction in municipal expenditures and an increase in municipal debt in municipalities more exposed to aggressive MNCs relative to those less exposed. We find no significant change in municipal GDP. In Panel B, we show that this effect is driven by municipalities which only increase trade tax rate, but not the property tax rate; i.e. those for which we find that exposure to aggressive MNCs leads to a reduction in the overall tax revenue. These results suggest that to keep the municipal GDP constant following the drop in the overall tax revenues, the municipality that is more exposed to aggressive MNCs has to decrease its expenditures and increase debt relative to a municipality that is not exposed to those aggressive MNCs.

There are two caveats that come with this analysis. First, the GDP and debt data available to us do not cover the full set of municipalities. Second, the apportionment of tax revenues from state and federal governments to municipalities and vice versa could affect these estimates. While we show that the apportionment does not affect the responsiveness of trade tax revenues to changes in trade tax rates, this may not be the case for local expenditures. Given the two caveats, these results should be treated with caution. This is also why we do not interpret the magnitudes of the effects that trade tax rate increases have on debt and GDP, especially in relation to changes in tax revenues.

8 Discussion

This paper provides novel estimates of how tax revenue structures are affected by the profit-shifting practices of MNCs. In particular, we provide causal evidence that the exposure to more aggressive MNCs reduces the local capacity to collect tax revenues from those firms and, consequently, affects the tax revenue structure. Our findings have implications for local governments that are trying to increase their revenues from MNCs. We find that increasing trade tax rates in municipalities that have a large presence of aggressive firms has the opposite of the expected effect and reduces these revenues. We provide indicative evidence that increasing property tax rates in conjunction with trade tax rates prevents the loss of the overall tax revenue, but changes the structure of where these revenues come from.

Consequently, our findings point to a new channel—tax revenue structure—through which corporate tax avoidance might affect within-country income inequality. To the extent that corporate taxation and property taxation differ in their tax incidence, corporate tax avoidance

may have distributional effects. If the incidence of corporate taxation is more progressive than that of property taxation, municipalities with a large presence of aggressive firms that choose to increase their property tax rates together with trade tax rates could be increasing income inequality. Exploring the consequences of tax avoidance on tax incidence at the local level is a promising area of future research.

Our findings also suggest that aggressive MNCs may constrain the types of fiscal policies available to municipalities. By moving profits away from municipalities after trade tax rate increases, aggressive MNCs may induce municipalities to use other tax instruments or reduce spending. This previously unrecognised cost of corporate tax avoidance may be important to local governments. Further, our findings imply a potential additional benefit of policies that aim to reduce profit shifting opportunities, such as, for example, global minimum tax, for municipal governments. These policies could bring a higher autonomy in tax revenue structure for local governments, in addition to the other, more global, benefits such as lower differences in effective taxation between avoiding and non-avoiding firms.

Finally, it is worth noting that in comparison to municipalities, more instruments are available to governments at the country level. Those include, for example, personal, indirect, payroll, or property tax rates, as well as tax bases. At the country level, governments have not only a wider variety of tax instruments, but also borrowing capacity and flexibility, at their disposal to make changes that would compensate for the corporate tax revenues lost due to profit shifting. As such, one may expect that country governments may be more successful in maintaining the overall tax revenue constant relative to municipal governments without relying on potentially regressive types of taxes.

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Tables and figures

Table 1: Difference-in-Differences Results: pre and post Trade Tax Rate Increase

Panel A: Shares							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	log(trade tax rate)	log(property tax rate)	ln(trade tax rev)	trade tax share	ln(tot tax rev)	ln(prop tax rev)	property tax share
post=1	0.044*** (0.001)	0.039*** (0.002)	0.031** (0.013)	0.006** (0.003)	0.009* (0.005)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.002*** (0.001)
high agg share=1 × post	-0.004** (0.002)	0.003 (0.004)	-0.062*** (0.018)	-0.020*** (0.005)	-0.021** (0.010)	0.007** (0.003)	0.005*** (0.001)
Panel B: counts							
post=1	0.0438*** (0.001)	0.0400*** (0.002)	-0.0022 (0.012)	0.0085*** (0.002)	-0.0418*** (0.005)	0.0005 (0.001)	0.0025*** (0.001)
nb agg subs × post=1	-0.0004*** (0.000)	-0.0004 (0.001)	-0.0035*** (0.001)	-0.0006* (0.000)	-0.0014*** (0.000)	-0.0000 (0.000)	0.0003*** (0.000)
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	56992	63245	55952	44774	45028	56739	44918
Mean	2.513	2.462	5.893	0.303	7.295	5.342	0.151

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. The dependent variable in column 1 is the logarithm of the trade tax rate, in column 2, the logarithm of the property tax rate (average of property tax rates A and B), in column 3, the logarithm of trade tax revenue, in column 4, the share of trade tax revenue in all tax revenue, in column 5, the logarithm of total tax revenue, in column 6, the logarithm of property tax revenue (total of revenues from property tax rates A and B), and in column 7, the share of property tax revenue in all tax revenue. In Panel A, high agg share is a dummy equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs is larger than a median across all municipalities, in Panel B, nb agg subs is the number of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality across all specifications, and in columns 3-7 they further include trade tax and property tax rates (both property tax rate A and B separately). Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Figure 1: Dynamic Effects of the Tax Rate Increase on Municipal Revenue Structure

Note: In each panel we plot the event study coefficient estimates for the effects of trade tax rate increases for municipalities with a low share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs (low exposure munis) relative to control group and for municipalities with a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs (high exposure munis). The high exposure to aggressive MNCs is defined as above median and the coefficients are plotted in blue diamonds, while low exposure coefficients are plotted in red circles. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using the difference-in-differences methodology, the darker shaded box represents the 95% confidence interval, while the lighter shaded box, the 90% confidence interval. Panel (a) considers the effects on trade tax rates, Panel (b) on trade tax revenues, panel (c) on total tax revenues and panel (d) on the share of trade tax revenue in total tax revenue. In each specification we include municipality and state \times year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Figure 2: Dynamic Effects of Tax Rate Hikes on Real Firm Presence.

Note: This figure reports the dynamic effects of the trade tax rate increase on municipal aggregates of firm employment, total assets, turnover, and firm numbers. Each panel plots event study coefficients for municipalities with high exposure to aggressive MNCs (blue diamonds) relative to the control group and for municipalities with low exposure to aggressive MNCs (red circles) relative to the control group from 3 years before the tax rate increase to 3 years after the tax rate increase. The high exposure to aggressive MNCs is defined as above median. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using the difference-in-differences methodology, the darker shaded box represents the 95% confidence interval, while the lighter shaded box, the 90% confidence interval. In each specification, we include state \times year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include trade tax rate, property tax rate (both property tax rate A and B separately), municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality (with the exception of regressions with firm counts as the outcome variable, where we do not control for that). Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level. The sample time period includes years 2012—2019 for which we have observations of firm financial data.

Table 2: Difference-in-Differences Results: using real business operation weights

Panel A: Logarithm of trade tax revenue				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	share assets	share empl	share turnover	share profits
post=1	0.029** (0.013)	0.039*** (0.012)	0.043*** (0.013)	0.027** (0.013)
post=1 × agg MNC share	-0.092* (0.050)	-0.355*** (0.097)	-0.216*** (0.067)	-0.092** (0.039)
Panel B: Share of trade tax revenue				
post=1	0.010*** (0.003)	0.010*** (0.003)	0.012*** (0.003)	0.009*** (0.003)
post=1 × agg MNC share	-0.025** (0.012)	-0.030* (0.017)	-0.024* (0.013)	-0.019* (0.011)
Panel C: Logarithm of total tax revenue				
post=1	0.015 (0.009)	0.016* (0.008)	0.021** (0.009)	0.006 (0.010)
post=1 × agg MNC share	-0.114*** (0.037)	-0.233*** (0.078)	-0.152*** (0.044)	-0.044* (0.026)
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality controls	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	26165	25751	23339	25991

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. The dependent variable in all columns in Panel A is the logarithm of trade tax revenue, in Panel B the share of trade tax revenues in all municipal revenues, and in Panel C, the logarithm of total municipal tax revenue. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. Agg MNC share is the share of assets, employment, turnover, and profits that subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs hold in each municipality relative to assets, employment, turnover, and profits reported by all firms in that municipality. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include trade tax rate, property tax rate (both property tax rate A and B separately), municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Figure 3: Difference-in-difference: robustness tests

Note: This figure tests the robustness of the difference-in-differences coefficients in Table 1. In each case, we plot the interaction term between the high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs and post dummy. Panel A uses as a dependent variable the logarithm of trade tax revenues, panel B uses the logarithm of property tax revenue, panel C uses the share of trade tax revenue in total tax revenue, and panel D uses the logarithm of total tax revenue. The high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs is defined as above median. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using the difference-in-differences methodology and each shape corresponds to a different robustness test. The lines represent the 90% confidence intervals. Solid diamonds replicate directly coefficients from Table 1, squares show the results when we include all tax rate increases, triangles show the results when we weight the regression by municipal population, crosses show the results when we control for neighbouring tax rates, pluses show the results when we replace trade tax revenues with trade tax revenues minus apportionment (only in Panel a), red diamonds show results for baseline case, but for a high share of foreign MNCs in each municipality, blue diamonds show results for baseline case, but for a high share of domestic MNCs in each municipality, circles show baseline results in which instead of using a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs in each municipality, we calculate the share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs in all MNCs in each municipality and present the coefficient on the interaction between that and post=1 dummy. In each specification, we include state \times year and municipality fixed effects and control for trade tax rate, property tax rate (both property tax rate A and B separately), municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Table 3: The role of property tax rate changes.

Panel A: Both trade and property rate increases					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	ln(trade tax rev)	trade tax share	ln(tot tax rev)	ln(prop tax rev)	property tax share
post=1	0.075*** (0.021)	0.024*** (0.005)	0.026*** (0.009)	0.040*** (0.003)	0.002 (0.001)
high agg share=1 × post	-0.058** (0.028)	-0.021** (0.008)	-0.007 (0.018)	0.021*** (0.006)	0.007*** (0.002)
Observations	18090	14518	14644	18450	14585
Mean	5.471	0.286	6.909	5.082	0.164
Panel B: Only trade rate increases					
post=1	0.045** (0.020)	0.012*** (0.004)	0.024*** (0.009)	-0.000 (0.003)	-0.004*** (0.001)
high agg share=1 × post	-0.079*** (0.029)	-0.012* (0.007)	-0.047*** (0.015)	0.011 (0.007)	0.011*** (0.002)
Observations	36930	29256	29420	37460	29376
Mean	6.116	0.317	7.473	5.469	0.147
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. In Panel A, we consider cases when both trade and property tax rates change, while in panel B only cases when trade tax rates change. The dependent variable in column 1 is the logarithm of trade tax revenue, in column 2, the share of trade tax revenue in all tax revenue, in column 3, the logarithm of total tax revenue, in column 4, the logarithm of property tax revenue (the sum of revenue from property tax A and B), and in column 5, the share of property tax revenue in all tax revenue. high agg share is a dummy equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs is larger than a median across all municipalities. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include municipal population, the number of firms in each municipality, trade tax and property tax rates (both property tax rate A and B separately). Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Table 4: Expenditures, Debt, and GDP.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	log(gross exp)	log(GDP)	log(debt)	log(gross exp)	log(GDP)	log(debt)
Panel A: all municipalities						
nb agg subs	-0.002***	-0.000	0.003**			
× post=1	(0.001)	(0.000)	(0.001)			
high agg share=1				-0.008	0.007	0.047*
× post=1				(0.014)	(0.008)	(0.026)
Observations	36055	1240	1020	29452	828	686
Mean	7.875	15.852	12.679	7.891	15.808	12.517
Panel B: municipal heterogeneity						
	both rates increase			only trade tax rate increases		
nb agg subs	-0.001	0.000	0.001	-0.003***	-0.001	0.005**
× post=1	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.002)	(0.001)	(0.001)	(0.003)
Observations	33233	1072	876	17855	636	520
Mean	7.866	15.831	12.668	8.174	15.879	12.451
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. In Panel A, we include all municipalities, while in Panel B we look separately at municipalities that experience a trade tax and property tax rate increase at the same time (columns 1-3) and those that experience only the trade tax increase (columns 4-6). The dependent variable in columns 1 and 4 is the logarithm of gross expenditures, in columns 2 and 5 the logarithm of GDP, in columns 3 and 6 the logarithm of debt. High agg share is a dummy equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs is larger than a median across all municipalities, nb agg subs is the number of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNC. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include trade tax rate, property tax rate, municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality across all specifications. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

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Janský

Appendices

A Additional empirical results

Table A1: Difference-in-Differences Results: pre and post Tax Rate Increase, placebo

Panel A: Shares					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	ln(trade tax rev)	trade tax share	ln(tot tax rev)	ln(prop tax rev)	property tax share
post=1	0.027 (0.017)	0.008** (0.003)	-0.001 (0.006)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.002** (0.001)
high share=1 × post	-0.013 (0.019)	-0.010** (0.004)	0.014* (0.008)	0.009*** (0.002)	0.001 (0.001)
Panel B: counts					
post=1	0.023* (0.012)	0.002 (0.003)	0.007 (0.005)	0.001 (0.002)	-0.002** (0.001)
nb subs × post	-0.000** (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	-0.000** (0.000)	-0.000*** (0.000)	0.000* (0.000)
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	55934	44762	45016	56731	44925
Mean	5.893	0.303	7.294	2.820	0.021

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. The dependent variable in column 1 is the logarithm of trade tax revenue, in column 2, the share of trade tax revenue in all tax revenue, in column 3, the logarithm of total tax revenue, in column 4, the logarithm of property tax revenue, and in column 5, the share of property tax revenue in all tax revenue. In Panel A, high share is a dummy equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries that belong to MNCs is larger than a median across all municipalities, in Panel B, nb subs is the number of subsidiaries that belong to MNC. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include municipal population, the number of firms in each municipality, and trade tax and property tax rates. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Figure A1: Dynamic Effects of the Tax Rate Decreases on Municipal Revenue Structure

Note: In each panel we plot the event study coefficient estimates for the effects of trade tax rate decreases for municipalities with a low share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs (low exposure munis) relative to control group and for municipalities with a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs (high exposure munis). The high exposure to aggressive MNCs is defined as above median and the coefficients are plotted in blue diamonds, while low exposure coefficients are plotted in red circles. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using the difference-in-differences methodology, the darker shaded box represents the 95% confidence interval, while the lighter shaded box, the 90% confidence interval. Panel (a) considers the effects on trade tax rates, Panel (b) on trade tax revenues, panel (c) on total tax revenues and panel (d) on the share of trade tax revenue in total tax revenue. In each specification we include municipality and state \times year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Table A2: The Effect of Tax Rate Hikes on Real Firm Presence and tax competition.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	<i>Real firm operations</i>			<i>Tax competition</i>		
	employment	total assets	turnover	muni wage tax	ln(avg nghb trade tax rate)	ln(avg nghb prop tax rate)
post=1	-0.008 (0.022)	-0.061*** (0.017)	-0.041 (0.055)	-0.005** (0.003)	0.004*** (0.001)	0.002 (0.002)
high agg share=1 × post=1	0.024 (0.031)	0.070** (0.030)	0.106 (0.066)	0.000 (0.005)	0.000 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.004)
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Firm controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	23052	27435	15678	43768	22887	22887
Mean	5.320	10.186	10.751	8.620	2.515	2.421

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. The dependent variable in column 1 is the logarithm of the aggregated firm-level number of employees, in column 2 the logarithm of aggregated firm-level total assets, in column 3, the logarithm of aggregated firm-level turnover, in column 4 the logarithm of the municipal wage and income tax, in column 5 is the logarithm of the average trade tax rate of nearest 5 municipalities, in column 6 is the logarithm of the average property tax rate of nearest 5 municipalities. High agg share is a dummy equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs is larger than a median across all municipalities. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include trade tax rate, property tax rate, municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality across all specifications. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Table A3: The Goodman-Bacon decomposition

Dep Var.		Timing groups	Always vs timing	Never vs timing	Overall coefficient
Ln(trade tax revenues)	Coefficient	0.019	0	-0.087	-0.084***
	Weights	0.028	0	0.972	
Ln(property tax revenues)	Coefficient	0.074	0.137	0.055	0.056***
	Weights	0.028	0.000	0.972	
Ln(total tax revenue)	Coefficient	0.007	-0.039	-0.033	-0.032***
	Weights	0.021	0.000	0.979	
trade tax share	Coefficient	-0.013	0.010	-0.017	-0.016***
	Weights	0.021	0.000	0.979	
property tax share	Coefficient	0.007	0.015	0.017	0.016***
	Weights	0.021	0.000	0.979	

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. This table decomposes the overall effect of the trade tax increases using the Goodman-Bacon decomposition, based on balanced data during 2008-2019. This limits the number of observations, relative to the benchmark results, which is necessary to perform the decomposition. We report the estimated effects of the reform for the municipalities with a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs on the logarithms of trade tax revenues, property tax revenues, total tax revenues and then on the shares of trade tax and property tax revenues relative to total tax revenues. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In the decomposition, we include year and municipality fixed effects, but no controls. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Figure A2: Dynamic Effects of the Tax Rate Increase on Municipal Revenue Structure: staggered difference-in-differences corrections

(a) Log of trade tax revenues

(b) Log of property tax revenues

Note: This figure reports the dynamic effects of the tax rate increase on the logarithm of trade tax and property tax revenue (panels a and b respectively). Both panels include the event study coefficient plots for municipalities with a high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs relative to those with a low share and relative to the control group from 3 years before the tax rate decrease to 2 or more years after the tax rate decrease. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using different correction methodologies, while each vertical line represents the associated 95% confidence intervals. The high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs is defined as above the median. In each specification, we include state \times year and municipality fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Figure A3: The effect of neighbouring tax rate increases on revenues of control group municipalities

Note: This figure reports the dynamic effects of the average neighbouring tax rate *increase* on the logarithm of trade tax, property tax, and total tax revenue of control group municipalities. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate that compare the evolution of tax revenues relative to the benchmark $t=-1$ period, the darker shaded box represents the 95% confidence interval, while the lighter shaded box 90% confidence interval. There is no control group here. In each specification, we include state \times year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include trade tax rate, property tax rate, municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

Table A4: Difference-in-Differences Results: size of municipality

Panel A: Large municipalities							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	log(trade tax rate)	log(property tax rate)	ln(trade tax rev)	trade tax share	ln(tot tax rev)	ln(prop tax rev)	property tax share
post=1	0.030*** (0.001)	0.049*** (0.003)	0.012 (0.008)	0.007*** (0.002)	-0.004 (0.004)	0.001 (0.002)	-0.002*** (0.001)
high agg share=1 × post=1	-0.005*** (0.002)	0.018*** (0.005)	-0.031** (0.012)	-0.011*** (0.004)	-0.017** (0.008)	0.004 (0.003)	0.004*** (0.001)
Observations	36484	40519	36417	28505	28500	36429	28478
Mean	2.534	2.479	7.574	0.366	8.672	6.672	0.139
Panel B: Small municipalities							
post=1	0.028*** (0.001)	0.035*** (0.002)	0.003 (0.014)	0.006** (0.003)	-0.029*** (0.005)	0.003** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.001)
high agg share=1 × post=1	0.003 (0.005)	0.006 (0.010)	-0.070 (0.050)	-0.025** (0.011)	-0.013 (0.022)	-0.006 (0.009)	0.005 (0.003)
State × Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Municipality controls	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	36136	40073	34886	27652	27953	35859	27818
Mean	2.509	2.448	4.252	0.237	5.954	4.143	0.171

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. In Panel A, we consider only large municipalities which are defined as above median in terms of size in 2008, the first year in our sample. In Panel B, we consider only small municipalities. The dependent variable in column 1 is the logarithm of the trade tax rate, in column 2, the logarithm of the property tax rate, in column 3, the logarithm of trade tax revenue, in column 4, the share of trade tax revenue in all tax revenue, in column 5, the logarithm of total tax revenue, in column 6, the logarithm of property tax revenue, and in column 7, the share of property tax revenue in all tax revenue. High agg share is a dummy equal to 1 if the share of subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs is larger than a median across all municipalities, post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. In each specification, we include state × year and municipality fixed effects. Controls include municipal population, and the number of firms in each municipality across all specifications, and in columns 3-7 they further include trade tax and property tax rates. Standard errors are clustered at the municipality level.

B Sample descriptives.

Table B1: Descriptive Statistics: Municipalities

	(1)	(2)	(3)	
	high agg share	low agg share	diff	t-stat
number of firms	2452.489	110.620	-2341.869***	-29.062
employment: Orbis	5345.651	166.745	-5178.906***	-35.483
total assets: Orbis	5110920.666	39545.006	-5071375.660***	-17.780
turnover: Orbis	2067419.440	35224.547	-2032194.893***	-22.902
profits: Orbis	48154.176	1339.168	-46815.009***	-30.418
avg trade tax rate	13.040	12.423	-0.616***	-40.702
avg property tax rate	12.216	11.852	-0.363***	-17.949
avg of neighbouring trade tax rate	12.951	12.457	-0.494***	-24.707
avg of neighbouring property tax rate	11.122	11.306	0.184***	6.940
population	72694.764	3350.501	-69344.263***	-28.464
share of trade tax in all tax	0.437	0.276	-0.161***	-103.571
log(trade tax revenue)	8.626	5.364	-3.262***	-194.357
log(property tax revenue)	3.878	2.677	-1.202***	-96.644
log(total tax revenue)	9.553	6.841	-2.712***	-165.150
log(income share trade tax revenue)	8.434	5.173	-3.261***	-194.113
log(apportionment trade tax revenue)	6.858	3.693	-3.165***	-190.682
log(GDP)	15.860	14.936	-0.923***	-19.280
log(debt)	12.457	11.922	-0.535***	-6.189
Observations	17684	85659	103343	

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. We compare characteristics of municipalities across 2008—2019. Column 1 shows the means for municipalities with a higher share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs and column 2 shows the means for municipalities with a lower share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs. The high share of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs is defined as above the median across all municipalities in the sample.

Table B2: Orbis Data Coverage: Counts and Financials

Stats	total assets (1)	employment (2)	turnover (3)	profits (4)	firm count (5)	MNC count (6)
Panel A: firm coverage						
Mean	0.024	0.022	0.019	0.022	37,069	689
Median	0.023	0.021	0.018	0.021	2,820	53
Standard Deviation	0.010	0.010	0.009	0.010	70,217	1,256
Panel B: MNC coverage						
Mean	0.346	0.341	0.328	0.319		
Median	0.338	0.333	0.329	0.314		
Standard Deviation	0.154	0.153	0.153	0.148		

Note: Data from Orbis. This table summarises the data coverage in Orbis. Columns 1-4 show the fraction of firms that have financial data coverage for total assets, employment, turnover, and profits, respectively. Column 5 shows the average number of firms and column 6 the average number of multinational subsidiaries across municipalities. Panel A shows these statistics for overall firm coverage and Panel B for multinational firms only.

Figure B1: Distribution of the number of MNCs and shares of MNCs across municipalities.

(a) Shares of MNC subsidiaries

(b) Numbers of MNC subsidiaries

Note: This figure plots the distribution of the shares of MNC subsidiaries and the number of MNC subsidiaries across municipalities. In panel A, in blue, we plot the shares of subsidiaries belonging to MNCs across municipalities, and in red, the shares of subsidiaries belonging to aggressive MNCs across municipalities. In panel B, we plot the corresponding numbers of subsidiaries that belong to MNCs (in blue) and those that belong to aggressive MNCs (in red). In both panels, we omit zero shares and zero numbers municipalities for clarity of exposition. 71.7% of municipalities have no subsidiaries that belong to MNCs, and 83.6% of municipalities have no subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs.

Figure B2: Distribution of the share of assets, employment and turnover of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs across municipalities.

(a) Share of total assets

(b) Share of employment

(c) Share of turnover

Note: This figure plots the distribution of the shares of total assets, employment, and turnover that subsidiaries of MNCs own across municipalities in Panels a, b, and c, respectively. In each panel, in blue, we plot the shares belonging to MNCs, and in red, the shares belonging to aggressive MNCs. In both panels, we omit zero shares for clarity of exposition. 80% of municipalities have no assets that belong to subsidiaries of MNCs, and 93.5% of municipalities have no assets that belong to subsidiaries of aggressive MNCs.

Figure B3: Distribution of tax rate changes: numbers and sizes.

(a) Number of trade tax rate changes

(b) Size of trade tax rate changes.

(c) Number of property A tax rate changes

(d) Number of property B tax rate changes

(e) Size of property tax rate changes.

Note: In panels a, c and d, we plot the number of times a tax rate changed in each municipality across the sample period: 2008 - 2019. In blue, we have the tax rate increases, and in red, the tax rate decreases. We exclude cases when the tax rate did not change at all. In Panels b and e, we plot the distribution of the sizes of these tax rate changes. In Panels a and b, we focus on changes in trade tax rates and in panels c-e on changes in property tax rates.

Table B3: Number of property and trade tax rate changes.

	obs	avg prop A rate ch	avg prop B rate ch	avg trade rate ch
Panel A: all municipalities				
property tax A & B, trade tax	6,091	0.98	1.12	0.66
property tax A, trade tax	281	0.49		0.35
property tax B, trade tax	1,018		1.02	0.54
trade tax	1,648			0.63
property tax A & B	2,871	1.02	1.05	
property tax A	374	0.78		
property tax B	1,340		1.06	
Panel B: more exposed to aggressive MNCs				
property tax A & B, trade tax	1353	0.8	0.97	0.41
property tax A, trade tax	119	0.32		0.15
property tax B, trade tax	277		1.06	0.4
trade tax	373			0.47
property tax A & B	513	1.04	1.17	
property tax A	94	0.86		
property tax B	366		1.19	
Panel C: less exposed to aggressive MNCs				
property tax A & B, trade tax	4738	1.03	1.16	0.73
property tax A, trade tax	162	0.62		0.5
property tax B, trade tax	741		1	0.59
trade tax	1276			0.68
property tax A & B	2358	1.01	1.02	
property tax A	280	0.76		
property tax B	974		1	

Note: This table summarises the tax rate changes during our sample period. In Panel A, we summarise these changes for all municipalities, in Panel B, only for those that we identify as being more exposed to aggressive MNCs and in Panel C, only for those that we identify as being less exposed to aggressive MNCs. In each panel, we show the total number of times that trade tax rate changes alone or in conjunction with property tax rates. We also show the average rate change in each of those cases.

Figure B4: Number of Subsidiaries Across Municipalities

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. This maps outlines all German municipalities and the number of firms in each.

Figure B5: Number of Subsidiaries that belong to Multinationals across Municipalities

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. This maps outlines all German municipalities and the number of subsidiaries of multinational firms in each.

Figure B6: Number of Subsidiaries that belong to Aggressive Multinationals Across Municipalities

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. This maps outlines all German municipalities and the number of subsidiaries that belong to aggressive multinationals in each. Aggressive multinational subsidiary is defined as a subsidiary belonging to a firm that owns a tax haven subsidiary as well.

Figure B7: Trade tax rates.

Note: Data from German Statistical Office. This maps outlines all German municipalities and the trade tax rates variation across municipalities in 2014.

Figure B8: Property tax rates.

Note: Data from German Statistical Office. This maps outlines all German municipalities and the property tax rates variation across municipalities in 2014. Property tax rate is the average of property tax rates A and B.

C Firm level results.

Table C1: Profitability and real operations: firm-level results.

	<i>Profits</i>			<i>Real operations</i>			
Panel A: Firm-level clustering							
	(1) ROA	(2) ETR	(3) log(tax)	(4) log(assets)	(5) log(fxa)	(6) log(empl)	(7) log(turnover)
post=1	0.003 (0.002)	0.001 (0.004)	-0.002 (0.033)	-0.010* (0.005)	-0.032*** (0.007)	-0.005 (0.005)	-0.014 (0.009)
MNC \times post=1	0.008 (0.007)	0.029** (0.012)	0.292*** (0.096)	0.108*** (0.019)	0.187*** (0.026)	0.057*** (0.014)	0.039 (0.037)
MNC \times post=1 \times agg	-0.020* (0.012)	-0.057*** (0.021)	-0.332* (0.192)	-0.031 (0.040)	-0.074 (0.066)	-0.019 (0.038)	-0.041 (0.065)
Panel B: Municipal- and year-level clustering							
post=1	0.003 (0.003)	0.001 (0.004)	-0.002 (0.054)	-0.010 (0.007)	-0.032*** (0.009)	-0.005 (0.006)	-0.014 (0.013)
MNC \times post=1	0.008** (0.004)	0.029 (0.017)	0.292** (0.104)	0.108*** (0.030)	0.187*** (0.034)	0.057*** (0.016)	0.039 (0.047)
MNC \times post=1 \times agg	-0.020** (0.009)	-0.057** (0.020)	-0.332*** (0.100)	-0.031 (0.046)	-0.074 (0.059)	-0.019 (0.025)	-0.041 (0.072)
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Firm FEs	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	156761	131003	132575	294854	276316	173983	103193
# firms	35,581	30,804	30,876	49,005	46,316	40,670	26,340
Mean	0.496	0.492	0.492	0.484	0.482	0.481	0.506

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. This table reports the results from estimating the effects of municipal trade tax rate increases on subsidiary-level profits and real operations. In columns 1- 3, we consider effects on firm profits; the dependent variable in column 1 is the returns on assets, which is the ratio of profits and loss before tax to total assets, in column 2 the effective tax rate, which is the ratio of tax paid to profit and loss before taxes, in column 3 the logarithm of tax paid. In columns 4-7, we consider the effects on the firm's real operations; the dependent variable in column 4 is the logarithm of total assets, in column 5 is the logarithm of fixed assets, in column 6 is the logarithm of the number of employees, and in column 7 is the logarithm of turnover. Post is equal to 1 after the tax rate increase and 0 beforehand. It is also zero for all control group municipalities. Agg is a dummy equal to 1 when the MNC that owns that particular subsidiary has a tax haven subsidiary. In each specification, we include year and firm fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the firm level in panel A and the municipal-year level in Panel B.

Figure C1: Profitability and real-effects: firm-level event studies.

(a) ROA and ETR

(b) Log of tax paid.

(c) Real operations.

Note: Data from Orbis and German Statistical Office. This figure reports the dynamic effects of municipal trade tax rate increases on subsidiary-level profits and real operations. In Panel a, we consider the effects on returns on assets, which is the ratio of profits and loss before tax to total assets, and on the effective tax rate, which is the ratio of tax paid to profit and loss before taxes. In Panel b, we look at the logarithm of tax paid. In Panel c, we look across real operations, which we proxy by logarithms of total assets, fixed assets, number of employees, and turnover. All panels include the event study coefficient plots for subsidiaries that belong to aggressive MNCs relative to those that belong to non-aggressive MNCs and relative to the control group of domestic firms from 3 years before the tax rate increase to 2 or more years after the tax rate increase. An aggressive MNC is defined as one that has a tax haven in its ownership structure. Each dot represents the coefficient estimate using the difference-in-differences methodology, the darker shaded box represents the 95% confidence interval, while the lighter shaded box 90% confidence interval. In each specification, we include firm and year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the firm level.

Table C2: Tax haven subsidiaries and parents: firm-level coverage

country	subsidiary frequency	%	parent frequency	%
Andorra	7	0.03	9	0.04
Antigua and Barbuda	26	0.1		
Anguilla	6	0.02	1	0
Barbados	29	0.11	1	0
Bahrain	58	0.22	1	0
Bermuda	229	0.88	216	0.97
Bahamas	13	0.05	250	1.12
Belize	9	0.03	2	0.01
Switzerland	6,538	24.99	10,182	45.52
Costa Rica	91	0.35	1	0
Cyprus	464	1.77	268	1.2
Djibouti	2	0.01		
Dominica	7	0.03		
Micronesia	2	0.01		
Gibraltar	28	0.11	25	0.11
Hong Kong	2,854	10.91	296	1.32
Ireland	1,622	6.2	699	3.12
Jordan	53	0.2		
Saint Kitts and Nevis			1	0
Cayman Islands	717	2.74	1,215	5.43
Lebanon	47	0.18	46	0.21
Liechtenstein	43	0.16	1,017	4.55
Liberia	40	0.15	5	0.02
Luxembourg	8,412	32.15	7,688	34.37
Monaco	83	0.32	1	0
Marshall Islands	109	0.42	6	0.03
Macao	29	0.11		
Malta	560	2.14	11	0.05
Mauritius	287	1.1	3	0.01
Maldives	1	0		
Nauru	1	0		
Panama	180	0.69	11	0.05
Seychelles	6	0.02	6	0.03
Singapore	3,333	12.74	254	1.14
San Marino	12	0.05		
Tonga	1	0		
Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	2	0.01		
Virgin Islands (British)	256	0.98	135	0.6
Vanuatu	1	0	1	0
Samoa	6	0.02	17	0.08
	26,164		22,368	

Note:

Data

from

Orbis

BvD.